

Supporting information for:

Hard phase crystallization directs the phase segregation of hydrogen-bonded supramolecular polymers

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Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectra of hydroxyl terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) (PEB-OH) and of the products of the three-step synthesis of isophthalic acid terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) (**P1**).

Figure S2. Synthesis of bipyridines **a-f** (varying methylene spacer) and **g** (varying architecture).

Figure S3. ¹H NMR spectrum of **a** in CDCl₃.

Figure S4. ¹³C NMR spectrum of **a** in CDCl₃.

Figure S5. ESI-MS spectrum of **a**.

Figure S6. ¹H NMR spectrum of **b** in CDCl₃.

re S7. ¹³C NMR spectrum of **b** in CDCl₃.

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Figure S8. ESI-MS spectrum of **b**.

Figure S9. ^1H NMR spectrum of **c** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S10. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **c** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S11. ESI-MS spectrum of **c**.

Figure S12. ^1H NMR spectrum of **d** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S13. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **d** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S14. ESI-MS spectrum of **d**.

Figure S15. ^1H NMR spectrum of **e** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S16. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **e** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S17. ESI-MS spectrum of **e**.

Figure S18. ¹H NMR spectrum of **f** in CDCl₃.

Figure S19. ¹³C NMR spectrum of **f** in CDCl₃.

Figure S20. ESI-MS spectrum of **f**.

Figure S21. ¹H NMR spectrum of **g** in CDCl₃.

Figure S22. ¹³C NMR spectrum of **g** in CDCl₃.

Figure S23. ESI-MS spectrum of **g**.

Figure S24. DSC traces (first heating) of bipyridines **a-g**.

Figure S255. TGA traces of bipyridines **a-g**. The weight loss observed up to 100 °C is due to the loss of adsorbed water as the bispyridines are hygroscopic.

Figure S266. Azimuthally integrated SAXS spectra of bipyridines **a-g** measured at ambient temperature showing the lack of nanometer-scale ordered structures.

Figure S277. ^1H NMR spectra of **P1e** (10 mg/mL in $\text{C}_6\text{D}_5\text{Cl-d}_5$) recorded at 25, 35, 45, 55, 65 and 75 $^\circ\text{C}$. The spectra show the shift of (only) the signals of the aromatic protons situated in close proximity to the hydrogen bond as the temperature is increased.

Figure S28. POM micrograph of a solvent-cast film of **P1e** without additional thermal treatment (scale bar = 200 μm).

Figure S29. DMA traces showing the storage modulus (E') and $\tan \delta$ of crystallized **P1a** as a function of temperature; traces shown are representative of 3 independent measurements.

Figure S30. DMA traces showing the storage modulus (E') and $\tan \delta$ of crystallized **P1b** as a function of temperature; traces shown are representative of 3 independent measurements.

Figure S31. DMA traces showing the storage modulus (E') and $\tan \delta$ of crystallized **P1c** as a function of temperature; traces shown are representative of 3 independent measurements.

Figure S32. DMA traces showing the storage modulus (E') and $\tan \delta$ of crystallized **P1d** as a function of temperature; traces shown are representative of 3 independent measurements.

Figure S33. DMA traces showing the storage modulus (E') and $\tan \delta$ of crystallized **P1e** as a function of temperature; traces shown are representative of 3 independent measurements.

Figure S34. DMA traces showing the storage modulus (E') and $\tan \delta$ of **P1f** as a function of temperature; traces shown are representative of 2 independent measurements.

Figure S35. DMA traces showing the storage modulus (E') and $\tan \delta$ of crystallized **P1g** as a function of temperature; traces shown are representative of 3 independent measurements.

Table S1. Values of the thermal and mechanical properties of the SPs **P1a-P1g** and the mass fractions of their hard phase (IPA-Py) and soft phase (PEB).

	T_c [°C]	T_g [°C]	T_m [°C]	E' at 25 °C [MPa]	PEB / IPA-Py [mass fraction, %]
P1a	42	-55	56	10.5 ± 1.6	84.2 / 15.8
P1b	47	-53	78	7.2 ± 2.8	83.8 / 16.2
P1c	60	-52	70	9.4 ± 1.5	83.4 / 16.6
P1d	60	-50	72	5.2 ± 1.2	83.0 / 17.0
P1e	38	-52	55	27.7 ± 2.0	81.0 / 19.0
P1f	Ø	-52	Ø	1.3 ± 0.3	83.4 / 16.6
P1g	120	-51	130	6.4 ± 1.9	84.2 / 15.8

Figure S36. Creep experiments on a) **P1e**, b) **P1f** and c) **P1g** showing the evolution over time of stress under a constant strain of 2% at room temperature.

Figure S37. Time-lapse pictures of a qualitative creep experiment with films of supramolecular polymers **P1e**, **P1f** and **P1g**. The films hang clamped. One clamp serves to hold the films and the other acts as a light weight (ca. 2.8 g). The pictures show the films at 0 min, 45 min and 90 min. The pictures in the bottom show the films before and after the creep test.

Figure S38. Azimuthally integrated SAXS spectra of **P1a** measured at ambient temperature, at 45 °C (i.e., 10 °C below its T_m), at 65 °C (i.e., 10 °C above its T_m) and at 105 °C (i.e., 50 °C above its T_m). The first, second and third order scattering maxima are indicated.

Figure S39. Azimuthally integrated SAXS spectra of **P1b** measured at ambient temperature, at 68 °C (i.e., 10 °C below its T_m), at 88 °C (i.e., 10 °C above its T_m) and at 128 °C (i.e., 50 °C above its T_m). The first, second and third order scattering maxima are indicated.

Figure S40. Azimuthally integrated SAXS spectra of **P1c** measured at ambient temperature, at 60 °C (i.e., 10 °C below its T_m), at 80 °C (i.e., 10 °C above its T_m) and at 120 °C (i.e., 50 °C above its T_m). The first, second and third order scattering maxima are indicated.

Figure S41. Azimuthally integrated SAXS spectra of **P1d** measured at ambient temperature, at 62 °C (i.e., 10 °C below its T_m), at 82 °C (i.e., 10 °C above its T_m) and at 122 °C (i.e., 50 °C above its T_m). The first, second and third order scattering maxima are indicated.

Figure S42. Azimuthally integrated SAXS spectra of **P1e** measured at ambient temperature, at 45 °C (i.e., 10 °C below its T_m), at 65 °C (i.e., 10 °C above its T_m) and at 100 °C (i.e., 50 °C above its T_m). The first, second, third and fourth order scattering maxima are indicated.

Figure S43. Azimuthally integrated SAXS spectra of **P1f** measured at ambient temperature, at 68 °C, at 88 °C and at 128 °C. As **P1f** is an amorphous polymer, the temperatures selected are those used in the analysis of **P1b** due to their similar structure and hard phase mass fraction. The first, second and third order scattering maxima are indicated.

Figure S44. Azimuthally integrated SAXS spectra of **P1g** measured at ambient temperature, at 120 °C (i.e., 10 °C below its T_m), at 140 °C (i.e., 10 °C above its T_m) and at 180 °C (i.e., 50 °C above its T_m). The first, second and third order scattering maxima are indicated.

Table S2. Table listing the position on the q-scale of the scattering maxima (q_1 , q_2 , q_3 and q_4) of **P1a-P1g** extracted from the SAXS spectra at 25 °C, the calculated domain spacing (d), and the measured domain spacing extracted from the FFT measurements on TEM micrographs (d_{TEM}).

	q_1^* [nm ⁻¹]	q_2^* [nm ⁻¹]	q_3^* [nm ⁻¹]	q_4^* [nm ⁻¹]	d^{**} [nm]	d_{TEM}^{***} [nm]
P1a	0.8	1.3	1.5	2.0	8.3	8.4 ± 0.4
P1b	0.7	1.2	1.9	2.4	8.9	8.7 ± 0.8
P1c	0.9	1.5	1.9		7.2	8.6 ± 0.4
P1d	0.8	1.8	2.3		8.3	8.9 ± 0.9
P1e	0.7	1.4	2.0	2.7	9.1	9.5 ± 0.7
P1f	0.9	1.6	1.8		6.9	6.7 ± 0.3
P1g	0.9	1.6	1.9		6.7	6.8 ± 0.4

q^* decimal values round to one decimal; $d^{**} = (2\pi)/q_1$; d_{TEM}^{***} mean values extracted from FFT measurements on 3-4 images. The error is reported as max/min – mean. The value for P1c is slightly lower (7.8 ± 0.8 nm) if calculated as a mean of the values obtained from images showing the top and side-views of the hexagonally packed cylinders.

Table S3. Table listing the position on the q-scale of the scattering maxima (q_1 , q_2 and q_3) of **P1a-P1g** extracted from the SAXS spectra at T_m+10 °C for **P1b-P1g** and T_m+50 °C for **P1a** and the calculated domain spacing (d).

	q_1^* [nm ⁻¹]	q_2^* [nm ⁻¹]	q_3^* [nm ⁻¹]	d^{**} [nm]
P1a	1.0	1.7	2.0	6.2
P1b	1.0	1.7	2.0	6.5
P1c	1.0	1.7	2.0	6.3
P1d	1.0	1.7	1.9	6.5
P1e	1.0	1.7	1.9	6.5
P1f	1.0	1.7	1.2	6.6
P1g	1.0	1.7	1.9	6.5

q^* decimal values round to one decimal; $d^{**} = (2\pi)/q_1$;

Figure S45. a) Azimuthally integrated SAXS spectra of a mixture of the hydroxyl terminated poly(ethylene-co-butylene) (PEB-OH, 1eq.) with bipyridine **b** (2 eq.) measured at ambient temperature showing no structure at the nanoscale. b) POM micrographs of solution-casted PEB-OH/**b** mixture in the solid state showing macrophase segregation of the two components (bipyridine **b** demixes from PEB-OH and forms needle-like crystals) with direct light (top, scale bar = 100 nm) and under polarized light (bottom, scale bar = 100 μm).

Figure S46. Additional TEM micrographs of **P1a** a) scale bar = 100 nm, b) and c) scale bars = 50 nm.

Figure S47. Additional TEM micrographs of **P1b** a) scale bar = 100 nm, b) and c) scale bars = 50 nm.

Figure S48. Additional TEM micrographs of **P1c** a) scale bar = 50 nm, c) scale bar = 20 nm, b) scale bar = 50 nm.

Figure S49. Additional TEM micrographs of **P1d** a) scale bar = 100 nm, b) and c) scale bars = 50 nm.

Figure S50. Additional TEM micrographs of **P1e** a) and c) scale bars = 100 nm, b) scale bar = 200 nm.

Figure S51. Additional TEM micrographs of **P1f** a), b) and c) scale bars = 50 nm.

Figure S52. Additional TEM micrographs of **P1g** a) and b) scale bars = 50 nm, c) scale bar = 20 nm.